

UNIVERSITY AND DISTANCE EDUCATION: REALITIES OF EDUCATIONAL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Education undergoes changes that accompany technological innovations, such as Distance Learning, access to virtual libraries, communication of students and teachers through virtual social networks, use of applications, among others in the teaching-learning process. Thus, with a scenario in which information arrives at an ever-faster speed and with Education and its members being involved in this update, it is necessary to make adaptations in the way of teaching and learning in the face of the information society and cyberspace. . This work seeks to analyze how Distance Education is seen by the critical view of students in the modality.

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1. Introduction

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) inserted in teaching and learning methodologies have been marking current education. These are changes that must occur in order

to seek the decentralization of the teacher in the classroom and encourage the student to build knowledge collectively and collaboratively, with teacher action and mediation.

In this scenario, knowledge should not only come from the teacher, but together and in harmony with the students and their experiences, at which point they are mediated and adapted by the teacher. Assessment must also follow this line: as a continuous and cumulative performance process, with a view to the competences, abilities and attitudes of the student (COTTA, et al, 2012).

The objective of this work is to carry out a critical discussion of Distance Education from the point of view of two students of the teaching modality.

2. Contemporary Education

Contemporary Education emerges through changes on the part of teachers, students and the educational institution itself to adapt to the constant uses of ICTs in all environments. As mentioned by Cotta et al (2012, p. 788), “current trends in the field of education point to the use of active teaching-learning methodologies, aiming to make the student the protagonist of their own training process”.

As Freire (1975) defends, it is extremely important to change the paradigms of Education, where the traditional banking education, in which the teacher holds the truth and knowledge, transmitting it to the student, is transformed into a liberating education, by through the experiences and experiences of students. One of the forms of transformation can be carried out with the use of ICTs.

According to Silveira (2019, p.2), “technology should be an apparatus for improving, transforming and modernizing teaching, and not for transforming methodological structures and learning practices”. Likewise, learning and assessment instruments must be able to trigger a vision of the whole and also encourage the construction of networks of social change that enable the expansion of individual and collective consciousness (COTTA, et al, 2012).

3. The reality of Distance Education

Distance education demonstrates that resources such as interactive video classes, associated with good teaching material, are the ones that most reduce the transactional distance

between the educator and the student. The availability of other synchronous and asynchronous communication resources such as chat, discussion forum, among others, is also a strong ally in this cognitive process (MORAN, 2017).

The transactional distance can still be reduced when education systems also associate synchronous and asynchronous resources in the right measure and, preferably, dosed according to the cognitive profile of each student. In this context, the importance of communication in Education emerges.

Communication is a social fact, one of the elements that constitute the educational process, which leads to the realization of the educational process. Communication presents a set of procedures for connecting people, it is a transversal axis in educational practice between teachers and students.

Education and communication become necessary to adapt the service to the needs of teachers and students. Citelli (2010) reports that the growth in the participation of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in the social space reinforces this concern, as the means of communication also occupy school spaces.

4. Critical analysis of Distance Education

In the midst of the technological modernity we live in, it is only fair that we adapt the way of educating and training. The internet, used to connect people, is also being used to enable teaching beyond the school walls, in the virtual world, reaching more and more people through distance learning.

This method is highly inclusive and allows the student to adapt to the educational process, in a personalized way, meeting some of the needs of the public that wants to complete an educational stage.

This aspect aims to give access to more people who wish to study and become a professional but, for whatever reason, do not have contact with a university or even the time to go to it. It is encouraging to be able to work around problems such as distance and lack of time, which would exclude future students from the didactic universe, and insert them into the growing number of people benefiting from EaD.

It would be a perfect idea if there was no other side of the coin. There are several factors that do not contribute to the success of distance learning. Everyone involved in this medium

has their share of contribution for its success. Small mistakes can disrupt this process.

It is the responsibility of the student institution that offers EaD to provide software support, to provide teachers and tutors, to plan the course offered well in order to enable students to take better advantage of the activities.

Studying at home requires strategic time planning and extra dedication from the student. Periodically visiting the Moodle space is like keeping attendance in the face-to-face course, a student's duty.

It is the task of teachers to facilitate students' access to the didactic content and ensure that it is understood by them in unison. Tutors should encourage students to participate in activities and bridge the gap between professors and students.

5. Final comments

The development of information and communication technologies generate new work rhythms, new environments, new instruments, new languages or forms of expression. Thus, it becomes necessary to consider the media as objects of study, with their ethical and aesthetic aspects, and as pedagogical and didactic tools. This scenario of pedagogical action in online environments reveals that it is necessary to stop being mere spectators and start having a profile of "active participants".

It is necessary to create conditions for the development of media skills that favor communication, which promotes effective interaction between students and professors on the Web. -if you are using the most advanced technology to do the obvious or the traditional.

Thus, teaching and learning in the virtual environment comprises some similarities with the traditional way, such as the interaction between students and teacher, the need for reflection, analysis and interpretation of texts, information and what is taught. It is also necessary to emphasize that virtual education can be carried out at different levels of education, both primary, secondary and higher. The most important thing is that this teaching is a source of dialogue and attention both on the part of the teacher and the student, in addition to the necessary support from the Institution of Teaching, which should encourage and develop Distance Education and Education as a whole. Only in this way can a nation become strong and have well-educated citizens.

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